

SPACE ASTROMETRY (HIPPARCOS)

Further Details on the Scientific Data Processing

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1. Introduction

This note is intended as an aid for estimating the complexity and amount of data processing needed for the HIPPARCOS project. It complements in some respects two previous notes,

- /1/ "Processing of Data from the Astrometry Satellite", by Poder, Høgg, and Høyer (August 1979), and
- /2/ "Scientific Data Processing", by Lindegren (Section 3.6 of the ESTEC report PF616, December 1979).

/1/ and /2/ concentrate on the late stages of the scientific data processing, i.e. the so-called three-step procedure for reconstituting the celestial sphere, although /2/ contains a good deal of mathematical details pertaining to the earlier stages (treatment of raw data, i.e. photon counts, etc.).

A natural starting-point for this note is the data processing flow chart, Fig. 3.6.2 of /2/, here reproduced as Fig. 1 (with some small but significant modifications). This is complemented by a similar scheme for the on-board data handling, Fig. 2. Remember that rectangular boxes mean 'data files' (on magnetic tapes, discs, computer memory, or whatever), while oval boxes indicate 'procedures'.

One way to define what the data processing really means is to describe the data files at the different points of the processing scheme: since the input and output of any procedure is a set of data files, these define uniquely what is required from the procedure. After having described the on-board data handling (Section 2), I have therefore attempted to describe, as accurately as possible, most of the data files in the upper part of Fig. 1 (Section 3). As a by-product, this gives of course fairly accurate estimates of the file sizes. In Section 4, some of the procedures in the early stages of the reductions are described from a more practical point of view than was done in /2/. In particular, I have tried to estimate computing requirements in terms of storage and execution times. For one particularly critical procedure (the IDT data pre-processing) I have even given a formal mechanization of the basic algorithm (Appendix A and B), to facilitate an accurate evaluation of complexity and computing requirements.

FIG. 1. HIPPARCOS - Organization of scientific data processing.
 Numbers in some of the data file boxes indicate approx. sizes (tapes).

2. Description of observations and on-board data handling

The flow chart for the ground-based data handling, Fig. 1, is complemented by Fig. 2 showing the data handling on board the satellite. This is necessary for a description of the (hereby) proposed IDT observing strategy, which in turn is necessary for a detailed description of the IDT data used as input for processing on the ground.

2.1. Time hierarchy

The collection of data by the satellite will be governed by a sufficiently stable time base available on board, presumably provided by a quartz clock which is also timing the on-board computer (OBC). Although the clock frequency is probably of the order of 10 MHz, we are not concerned here with time intervals shorter than the photometric sampling interval, which is taken to be exactly 1/1200 sec both for the IDT and photomultiplier detection systems. For our purpose the natural time scale is thus the sequence of sampling intervals $t_0 + (k-1)/1200 \leq t < t_0 + k/1200$ sec, with $k = 1, 2, \dots, \sim 10^{11}$. Based on this scale we shall build a very rigid hierarchy of time scales, in such a way that different events (e.g. the repositioning of the instantaneous field of view, IFOV) can only occur at certain multiples of the basic interval.

The first level of the hierarchy is thus the sampling interval 1/1200 s.

The second level has a period of 24 samples or 0.02 sec. This is the period for repositioning the IFOV and sampling the gyros. During this interval a star image moves 3" on the grid. This is on one hand sufficiently long to provide independent positional information about the star (≈ 2.5 grid periods); on the other hand it is only 1/10 of the IFOV diameter, so we can accept that the IFOV is stationary during that period of time.

The third level has a period of 240 samples or 0.2 sec. The IFOV should be switched between the different stars within the field of view (FOV) in such a way that it returns periodically to a particular star every 0.2 sec. This eliminates most of the influence of attitude jitter having frequency < 5 Hz (above 5 Hz the amplitude of the jitter is very small).

The fourth and highest level of the time hierarchy is a 'frame', comprising 2400 samples or 2 sec. The pattern of switching the IFOV will remain constant within a frame, since 2 sec is about the average lifetime of any configuration of stars in the FOV (i.e., a star enters the FOV or disappears from it every other second, on the average).

2.2. IDT observations

The on-board computer (OBC) generates a series of commands to the IDT detection subsystem, which is part of the payload. We shall assume that each command is a triplet of integers (I_x , I_y , M), and that one command is issued every 20 ms (24 samples). I_x and I_y (each an integer between, say, 0 and 4000) are the nominal coil currents for IFOV positioning, i.e. simply rectangular coordinates within the FOV. In the payload, I_x and I_y will be corrected for electronic and optical distortion by means of a look-up table, and then converted to the actual (analogue) IDT deflection coil currents. The number M (say, 1 or 2) specifies detection mode: $M = 1$ means that IDT pulses corresponding to photoelectrons are to be counted (this photon counting mode is used for more than 95 % of the time, i.e. for stars fainter than magnitude 5); $M = 2$ means that the alternative mode of detection is used (to avoid count saturation and/or bit overflow, e.g. analogue/logarithmic detection). The command (I_x , I_y , M) means that for the next period of 24 samples the IFOV shall be positioned at (I_x , I_y) and the IDT signal detected in mode M .

The sequence of IDT commands will have a simple and fixed pattern during one frame (2 sec). This pattern (IDT Observation Schedule in Fig. 2) is determined by the OBC from the real-time satellite attitude and the on-board star catalogue, which lists the identification numbers, positions (to about 1"), magnitudes (to about 1 mag.), and priorities (e.g. on scale 0 to 7) of all programme stars which may enter the FOV within the next few minutes. The OBC identifies which stars will be visible throughout the next frame and computes the optimal distribution of observing time between them. Typically four stars will be visible. These are to be observed cyclically, i.e. A-B-C-D-A-B-C-D-A-B-C-D-A-B- ... -B-C-D, with a period (from A to next A) of 0.2 sec. Since the IFOV is repositioned only every 0.02 sec, the time must be distributed between the stars in multiples of 0.02 sec, which means that 10 different stars, at most, can be observed in a frame (in which case each star would receive the same observing time). In our example with four stars, the 240 samples in a cycle A-B-C-D may be distributed as follows:

star A:	$2 \times 24 = 48$	samples	
" B:	$4 \times 24 = 96$	"	
" C:	$3 \times 24 = 72$	"	(Table 1)
" D:	$1 \times 24 = 24$	"	
total : $10 \times 24 = 240$ samples			

Star D is given proportionately little time, either because it is a bright star or because it has low priority, or both. B may be a faint star or a

high-priority object. (Note that the priority of a given star may be different at different times when its data are up-linked to the on-board catalogue; the programme on ground picking out stars from the master catalogue should review the observing history of each star and modify its priority accordingly.)

Since I_x and I_y can be assumed to vary linearly with time within a frame (to the required accuracy of 1"), the sequence of IDT commands in a frame will be uniquely determined by a few numbers only, e.g. the table

4						
2	839	1201	3.14	0.11	1	
4	2162	1857	3.12	0.07	1	(Table 2)
3	240	3011	3.14	0.07	1	
1	1161	295	3.13	0.15	2	

The first number (4) is the number of stars to be observed. Then follows one line per star, giving the proportion observing time (in tenths, cf. Table 1), I_x , I_y of the star at the time of the first sample in the frame, their increments D_x , D_y per 24 samples, and finally the detection mode M . The observation schedule in Table 2 would produce the following sequence of IDT commands:

sample no.	I_x	I_y	M	Remark: star under observation
1 - 24	839	1201	1	A
25 - 48	842	1201	1	A
49 - 72	2168	1857	1	B
73 - 96	2171	1857	1	B
97 - 120	2174	1857	1	B
121 - 144	2178	1857	1	B
145 - 168	259	3011	1	C
169 - 192	262	3011	1	C
193 - 216	265	3012	1	C
217 - 240	1189	296	2	D
241 - 264	870	1202	1	A
265 - 288	874	1202	1	A
289 - 312	2199	1858	1	B
:	:	:	:	:
2329 - 2352	545	3018	1	C
2353 - 2376	548	3018	1	C
2377 - 2400	1471	310	2	D

(Table 3)

As indicated in Fig. 2, the IDT data transmitted to the ground may consist of an identification label containing star identification numbers etc. and the observation schedule (Table 2), followed by the 2400 photometric samples.

2.3. Star mapper (SM) observations

The star mapper grid consists of two slit systems: the vertical slit system, containing 8 slits normal to the nominal scanning direction, and the inclined slit system, containing 8 slits inclined by (say) 45° to the former system. The separation of slit centers is 3" (along the scan) in both systems. Thus, a star travels across either system in about 0.16 sec or 192 samples. A programme star will cross one system or the other every 8 sec (on the average); thus only about 2 % of the time is useful and the OBC must compute (from the real-time attitude and the on-board star catalogue) when a star is expected to enter one of the slit systems, start collecting photometric samples from the SM shortly before (to allow for attitude uncertainty), and transmit to the ground a string of about 220 samples together with an identification label.

Star mapper data for some of the stars (e.g. relatively bright, single stars) will be processed in a coarse way (e.g. Fourier transform) and compared with predicted transit times across the slit systems; the resulting error signals (O-C) are fed to the on-board attitude reconstitution algorithm in order to calibrate gyro biases. On a short time scale (< 1-2 min), real-time attitude is obtained by integrating gyro outputs.

2.4. Gyro observations

A gyro senses the spacecraft motion around one axis (the input axis) by means of the resulting precession of the gimbal about an output axis normal to the input and spin axes (Fig. 3). The gimbal is electromagnetically maintained at the null position by application of a pulsed torque current (digital rebalance system). The gyro output, consisting of the number of torque pulses per sampling interval, is thus in principle proportional to the rotation rate about the input axis integrated over the sampling interval. Individual torque pulses may correspond to increments of 0.01° or larger; the sampling frequency should not exceed 100 Hz. Three gyros (possibly four for redundancy) will give the incremental attitude motion in three axes.

FIG. 3. Single-Degree-of-Freedom Gyroscope Construction Geometry (from Spacecraft Attitude Determination and Control, ed. J.R. Wertz, Astrophysics and Space Science Library Vol. 73, 1978)

3. Description of data files

We shall attempt to define the data files in Fig. 1 in terms of the exact meaning of the data, a possible data format, and the total size of the file. Sizes will be measured in 'number of tapes', where 'one tape' = 40 Mbytes (1 byte = 1 character or an 8-bit word). 40 Mbytes is roughly what can be stored in a standard (2400 ft) magnetic tape at 1600 bpi (bytes per inch). Note that there are roughly $4 \cdot 10^7$ frames in 2.5 years; hence the convenient rule: "bytes per frame = tapes per mission".

3.1. IDT_data

The 'raw' IDT data is by far the largest single file. Compact storage is thus essential. Nevertheless, it is very desirable that each frame (2 sec observation) is self-contained and uniquely identified. Thanks to the rigid time hierarchy described above this is easily achieved by attaching a short identification label to each string of 2400 IDT samples. The label contains the following information:

	F	=	frame number ($F = 1, 2, \dots, \approx 4 \cdot 10^7$)
	m	=	number of stars observed ($0 \leq m \leq 10$)
repeated m times	}	i	= star identification number (e.g. SAO number, 6 decimal digits)
		p/f	= observation in preceding or following field
		T	= fractional observing time (in tenths, $1 \leq T \leq 10$)
		I _{x0}	= nominal coil current I _x at beginning of frame ($0 \leq I_{x0} \leq 4000$)
		I _{y0}	= nominal coil current I _y at beginning of frame ($0 \leq I_{y0} \leq 4000$)
		D _x	= increment of I _x per 24 samples
		D _y	= increment of I _y per 24 samples
	M	=	detection mode

Then follows a string of 2400 IDT counts (each an 8-bit number).

Table 4 gives an example of two consecutive frames (cf. Table 2).

The photometric samples take 2400 bytes per frame. The label contains about 100 character; counting (liberally) one byte per character we find the total size of the IDT data file: 2500 tapes.

Table 4. Example of possible format for IDT data file (two consecutive frames with identification labels; cf. Table 2).

```

21340841
 4
218402  p   2   839   1201   3.14   0.11   1
 89935  f   4  2162   1857   3.12   0.07   1
210031  f   3   240   3011   3.14   0.07   1
 18430  p   1  1161    295   3.13   0.15   2
001 003 002 005 001 002 000 003 ... (2400 counts)

```

```

21340842
 3
218402  p   3  1152   1205   3.13   0.10   1
210031  f   5   554   3020   3.13   0.06   1
 18430  p   2  1473    301   3.12   0.14   2
005 003 008 007 003 001 004 003 ... (2400 counts)

```

3.2. SM_data

One star mapper observation consists of a fixed number of consecutive samples from the SM photomultiplier. We may fix this number to 230 for the time being (cf. Section 2.3). Each observation may be transmitted to the ground with an identification label, containing the following information:

F, K = frame no. and sample no. within the frame for the first sample
 (F = 1, 2, ..., $\approx 4 \cdot 10^7$; K = 1, 2, ..., 2400)
 i = star identification number
 p/f = observation in preceding or following field
 v/i = observation on vertical or inclined slits
 M = detection mode
 y/n = observation used for real-time attitude determination (yes/no)

Then follows a string of 230 SM counts (each an 8-bit number).

Table 5. Example of possible format for SM observations (three consecutive observations).

21340845, 131
 89935 f v 1 n
 006 003 007 005 005 ... (230 counts)

21340845, 1960
 190108 p i 1 y
 008 004 008 008 005 ... (230 counts)

21340847, 1095
 89935 f i 1 n
 006 006 004 010 009 ... (230 counts)

·
 ·

One observation thus needs about 250 bytes; since there will be about $1.0 \cdot 10^7$ such observations per 2.5 years, the total size of the SM data file is 63 tapes.

12.

3.3. Gyro data

We shall assume that three gyroscopes are sampled at 50 Hz (e.g. synchronously with the IFOV repositioning). One sample may be an 8-bit binary number (with sign). The gyro readings may be collected in frames containing 100 readings per gyro and identified (and timed) by the IDT observation frame number. The data format may be as in Table 6.

Table 6. Example of format for gyro readings (two frames = 4 sec)

21340841				
-010	-002	021	}	100 lines
-012	000	025		
:	:	:		

21340842				
-011	-010	029	}	100 lines
-008	-010	028		
:	:	:		

There are about 310 bytes/frame; hence total size of gyro data file: 310 tapes.

3.4. Calibration data and instrument parameters

At the beginning of reductions, calibration data are exclusively nominal values or laboratory calibrations, e.g.:

- nominal instrument parameters (scale value, basic angle, ..)
- $v_1(n, \zeta)$ and $v_2(n, \zeta)$ = small-scale grid distortion (e.g. from microphotometer measurements), cf. eq. (3.6.2) in /2/
- g_{mn}, h_{mn} = polynomial coefficients for the large-scale optical and grid distortion, cf. (3.6.13) in /2/, e.g. for $0 \leq m, n \leq 4$. These are partly measured, partly calculated by raytracing.
- the position of the SM slit systems relative to the main grid (microdensitometer measurements).

Later in the reductions, the low-order distortion coefficients g_{mn} , h_{mn} will be updated from the Step-1 solutions and some critical coefficients (e.g. the scale value and basic angle) are treated as functions of time (e.g. one set of values per 12 hour observation period). Even so, the polynomial coefficients will require < 0.1 Mbyte. v_1 and v_2 are represented as tables with at most about 1000×1000 entries. Thus total size of calibration file < 1 tape.

3.5. IDT signal parameters

This is a compressed version of the raw IDT data (2500 tapes). Ideally, it should retain all the useful information of the raw data, so that there is no need at any stage of the subsequent reductions to go back to the raw data. According to /2/, Section 3.6.3.2, we may take as signal parameters the vector $\hat{\underline{b}}$ of fitted modified Fourier coefficients, its covariance matrix $\underline{G} = \underline{F}^{-1}$, and a goodness-of-fit measure such as χ^2 .

A frame will then contain the following data (cf. Section 3.1):

	F	=	frame number
	m	=	number of stars per frame
repeated m times	{	i	= star identification number
		p/f	= preceding or following field
		T	= fractional observing time
		M	= detection mode
		$\bar{n}, \bar{\zeta}$	= average field coordinates (to $\sim 1''$)
		$\hat{\underline{b}}$	= estimated parameter vector (5 elements)
		$\underline{G}$	= estimated covariance of $\hat{\underline{b}}$ (symmetric 5×5 matrix)
	χ^2	=	goodness of fit

$\bar{n}$, $\bar{\zeta}$, $\hat{\underline{b}}$, $\underline{G}$, and χ^2 make 23 numbers; four bytes per number is certainly sufficient with reasonable scaling. The average m is 3.6, which gives about 370 bytes per frame. Thus total size of IDT signal parameters file: 370 tapes.

It may be necessary to double this size estimate, since it is probably convenient to store the signal parameters both chronologically (i.e. in order of observation, as assumed above) and systematically (i.e. with all observations of the same star collected together).

14.

3.6. SM signal parameters

The pre-processing of the SM data in Table 5 may give the following data per SM observation:

F	=	frame number
i	=	star identification number
p/f	=	preceding or following field
v/i	=	observation on vertical or inclined slits
M	=	detection mode
y/n	=	used for real-time attitude determination (yes/no)
a_0^1	=	estimated background level
a_1^1	=	estimated star intensity
a_2^1	=	estimated transit time (samples from beginning of frame)
σ_2	=	m.e. of a_2^1
χ^2	=	goodness of fit

With four bytes for each of the last five parameters we have about 38 bytes per SM observation; hence total size of SM signal parameter file: 10 tapes.

3.7. Grid coordinates

This is an even more compressed version of the IDT signal parameters file; however, this compression requires input information which will be altered in the course of reductions (especially concerning double stars).

One frame will contain the following information:

	F	=	frame number
	m	=	number of stars observed
repeated m times {	i	=	star identification number
	p/f	=	preceding or following field
	$\bar{\alpha}, \bar{\delta}$	=	average field coordinates (to $\sim 1''$)
	a_0, a_1, a_2	=	estimated background and star intensity and grid coordinate
	$\sigma_0, \sigma_1, \sigma_2$	=	estimated m.e. of a_0, a_1, a_2
	χ^2	=	goodness of fit

This amounts to about 164 bytes per frame. However, it does not seem to be necessary to store, at a time, more of this data than needed for one set solution (Step 1), i.e. 12 hour observation = 21600 frames. This is about 0.1 tape.

3.8. Attitude data

The attitude information needed for the Step-1 solutions is the three-axis attitude with respect to the stellar reference frame at the mid-time of each frame. This is defined e.g. by the angles $(\alpha_z, \delta_z, \omega)$, giving the right ascension and declination (epoch 2000) of the nominal spin axis, and the anomaly (ω) of the rotation about the spin axis. Required precision is about 0.1" or better. For pre-processing of IDT data (to obtain IDT signal parameters) we also need the relative rotation about the nominal spin axis during the 2 sec interval of the frame, to 0.05" or better. This may be given as a polynomial expansion of the Euler angle ψ (defined by $\dot{\psi} = \dot{\omega} + \dot{\alpha}_z \sin \delta_z$) as function of sample number (K) within the frame ($K = 1, 2, \dots, 2400$):

$$\psi(K) = \psi_0 + \psi_1 K + \psi_2 K^2 + \dots$$

Not more than 6-8 terms should be needed, considering the bandwidth of the attitude control loop etc.

One frame will then contain the following data:

F = frame number
 α_z = R.A. (2000.0) of the nominal spin axis (fixed to telescope)
 δ_z = Decl. (2000.0) - " -
 ω = anomaly of rotation about z axis (cf. Fig. 3.6.1 in /2/)
 $\psi_0, \psi_1, \dots$ = polynomial coefficients for Euler angle ψ (max. 8 numbers)

This requires about 30 bytes per frame; thus total size of file: 30 tapes.

3.9. Star abscissae

A set of five consecutive scans (12 hour observation) contains observations of about $m_s = 1800$ stars. The output of Step 1 will include the following data per 12-hour set:

s = set number ($s = 1, 2, \dots, \sim 1830$)
 $F_{\min}, F_{\max}$ = first and last frame included
 α_r = R.A. (2000.0) of the adopted pole of Reference Great Circle
 δ_r = Decl. (2000.0) - " -
 m_s = number of stars in the set
 m_s times $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} i = \text{star identification number} \\ a_i = \text{star abscissa } (\alpha_i \text{ in /2/}) \\ o_i = \text{star ordinate } (z_{ri} \text{ in /2/}) \\ \sigma_a = \text{estimated m.e. of } a_i \end{array} \right.$

Required (numerical) precision of angles $\sim 10^{-5}$ arcsec, or six bytes per angle. This means 0.0014 tape per set or, for 1830 sets in 2.5 years, 3 tapes.

3.10. The catalogue

The master catalogue contains, at the beginning of the reductions, a priori astrometric and photometric data on the 100,000 programme stars and a record of the observing history of each star, accumulated with a delay of a few days after the observations. The catalogue is updated in the course of the reductions, so that the current status of a star (within the processing scheme) and the currently best estimate of its astrometric parameters are readily available at any point of the reductions. The updating must of course be non-destructive.

The catalogue may contain the following information per star:

- i = star identification number
 $i', i'', i''', \dots$ = cross references
 (α, δ, m) = approx. position and magnitude (e.g. for searching)
 j, k, l = categorisations (e.g. fundamental star; primary star; useful for attitude determination;)
 p = (global) priority number (fixed throughout mission)
 $\left. \begin{array}{l} (\alpha_0, \delta_0) \\ (\mu_\alpha, \mu_\delta) \\ \tilde{\omega}_0 \end{array} \right\}$ = (exact) a priori astrometric parameters (2000.0)
 $\dot{\mu}_\alpha, \dot{\mu}_\delta, \ddot{\mu}_\alpha, \ddot{\mu}_\delta, \dots$ = (or similar) derived data for facilitating the calculation of position at any epoch
 U, B, V, m, Sp = a priori magnitude and spectral data

 $mult$ = multiplicity (a priori)
 $\Delta m, \rho_0, \theta_0, \dot{\rho}, \dot{\theta}, \dots$ = additional a priori data on multiple stars

(Obs. hist.) = observational history (one entry per spin in which the star was observed); typically 80 entries (see below)

 $\left(\begin{array}{l} \alpha_1, \delta_1, \mu_{\alpha 1}, \mu_{\delta 1}, \tilde{\omega}_1, m_1 \\ \sigma_\alpha, \sigma_\delta, \sigma_{\mu\alpha}, \sigma_{\mu\delta}, \sigma_{\tilde{\omega}}, \sigma_m \end{array} \right)$ = first iteration a posteriori data

 $\vdots$
 $\left(\begin{array}{l} \cdot \quad \cdot \quad \cdot \quad \cdot \quad \cdot \quad \cdot \\ \cdot \quad \cdot \quad \cdot \quad \cdot \quad \cdot \quad \cdot \end{array} \right)$ = last iteration (~ 6 th) of a posteriori data

The (Obs. hist.) record may contain, for each entry (spin): the mid-time of observation (frame no.), the observing time (sec), quality of data, accumulated obs. time (i.e. up to and including this entry), and accumulated weight. About 1000 bytes (on the average) should suffice for this record.

The average size is then about 1500 bytes per star, or 150 Mbytes for the entire catalogue = 4 tapes. However, in contrast to all previous files, random access is essential; thus about 1 disc unit is needed for the catalogue. Access to the catalogue is required at nearly all stages of the reductions.

4. Description of procedures

4.1. IDT data pre-processing

This is a sequential processing of IDT data (Section 3.1), one frame at a time, with additional inputs from the attitude data file (3.8; again, one frame at a time) and a priori calibrations of the grid (3.4).

The signal parameters $\hat{b}$, $G = \text{Cov}(\hat{b})$, χ^2 are extracted from each set $\{N_k\}$ of photometric samples in a frame referring to one star. The parameter vector $\hat{b} = (\hat{b}_1, \hat{b}_2, \hat{b}_3, \hat{b}_4, \hat{b}_5)^t$ is the maximum-likelihood solution of the observation equations

$$N_k \sim b_1 + b_2 \cos(H_k - b_3) + b_4 \cos(2H_k - 2b_3) + b_5 \sin(2H_k - 2b_3),$$

where H_k is a reference modulation phase computed from the preliminary attitude ψ_k (see 3.8) and the a priori calibrations of the scale value and the orientation and small-scale distortions of the grid:

$$H_k = 2\pi \left\{ (g_{10} + g_{11}\zeta_k + 2g_{20}\eta_k)\psi_k + g_{01}\zeta_k \right\} + v_1(\eta_k, \zeta_k).$$

(Note that the inclusion of v_1 in H_k is a deviation from eq. (3.6.18) in /2/.)

Field coordinates η_k, ζ_k may be estimated from the nominal coil currents I_x, I_y , which are computable from I_{x0}, I_{y0}, D_x, D_y given with the IDT data.

Processing of one frame then consists of the following tasks (excluding checking routines etc.):

- (a) - Read IDT data and attitude data for one frame
- (b) - Expand compressed counts (if detection mode $M = 2$ for some star); flag suspected data (e.g. first sample after IFOV switching to new star)
- (c) - For $k = 1$ to 2400, compute ψ_k from attitude data, (η_k, ζ_k) from nominal coil currents, then grid distortions $v_1(\eta_k, \zeta_k)$ from look-up table, and finally H_k from formula above
- (d) - For each of the m stars in the frame, compute $\hat{b}$, G , and χ^2
- (e) - Write one frame of data on the IDT signal parameters file.

Computing requirements: Straight-forward counting of arithmetic operations indicates that task (c) will require the equivalent of about 120,000 single precision floating-point additions (without clever programming). The fourth task may be evaluated on the basis of a FORTRAN routine (Appendix A and B) which is a slight modification of a successfully implemented and tested

routine for a very similar purpose. Computing time is estimated to the equivalent of another 120,000 additions (viz. 30,000 per star). Quasi real-time processing, requiring < 2 sec processing per frame of data, is then marginally feasible with a fast minicomputer ($t_{\text{add}} \sim 5 \mu\text{s}$). Storage requirements are very modest, except if a very large table is needed for the grid distortion $v_1(n, \tau)$.

4.1. SM data pre-processing

Input data are the SM data described in Section 3.2, with a string of 230 photometric counts N_r^i , $r = 1, 2, \dots, 230$. Signal parameters a_0^i, a_1^i, a_2^i (Section 3.6) are estimated from observation equations

$$N_r^i \sim a_0^i + a_1^i I_u(r - a_2^i),$$

where $I_u(r)$ is an array (length ~ 260) with a normalized model light curve for one of the slit systems ($u = v, i$ for vertical and inclined system).

The pre-processing may consist of the following tasks, excluding checking routines etc.:

(a) - Expansion of compressed counts (if $M = 2$)

(b) - Search for an integer k near the expected location a^i , such that $g_k \equiv \sum_r N_r J_u(r - k) \leq 0$ and $g_{k+1} > 0$. $J_u(r)$ is the auxiliary array

$$J_u(r) \equiv \frac{dI_u(r)}{dr} / I_u(r).$$

(c) - A first estimate of a_0^i, a_1^i, a_2^i is obtained from

$$a_2^i = k + g_k / (g_{k+1} - g_k)$$

$$a_1^i = (g_{k+1} - g_k) / A$$

$$a_0^i = (\sum_r N_r - B a_1^i) / 230$$

$$\sigma_2^2 = (A a_1^i + C a_0^i) / (A a_1^i)^2,$$

where

$$A \equiv \sum_r I_u(r) \left[J_u(r) \right]^2, \quad B \equiv \sum_r I_u(r), \quad C \equiv \sum_r \left[J_u(r) \right]^2.$$

(d) - Compute residual array $R_r = N_r - a_0^i - a_1^i I_u(r - a_2^i)$, using linear interpolation of I_u , $\chi^2 = \sum_r R_r^2 / N_r$, and (if needed) improve the estimate by one iteration of the likelihood equations.

Computing requirements: Tasks (b) - (c) require the equivalent of about 3000 additions (with a good searching strategy for (b) not more than five evaluations of g_k should be needed). Task (d) may require about 5000 additions (including one iteration); thus, with $t_{\text{add}} \sim 5 \mu\text{s}$, the complete procedure may take ~ 0.1 sec per SM observation (cf. mean time between SM observations ~ 8 sec).

4.3. Attitude reconstitution

Input for the off-line attitude reconstitution is the gyro reading, the SM signal parameters, and star positions computed from the catalogue (using orbital data for aberration). The reconstitution will be made twice: the first time shortly after the observations (a few days), using a priori star positions with an accuracy of $0.5 - 1''$ typically. This first attitude determination is used for the IDT data pre-processing (dashed line in Fig. 1) and for the first pass (iteration) of the three-step spherical reconstitution. The second attitude determination makes use of the improved star positions ($0.01'' - 0.02''$) after the first pass of the three-step procedure, and is thus possible only after completed mission. This improved (and in fact final) attitude is used in the following passes of the three-step procedure, but the IDT pre-processing will not be repeated with this attitude information.

The off-line attitude determination should be realized as a smoother, i.e., the attitude at any time t_0 is estimated using both past data ($t \leq t_0$) and future data ($t > t_0$). This is of course not possible for the real-time attitude determination aboard the satellite (needed for IDT piloting); that must be realized as a filter, i.e. using only past information ($t \leq t_0$). The difference between a filter and a smoother for the present purpose is illustrated in Fig. 4.

Although a smoother can in principle be realized (as suggested by Fig. 4) as the optimal combination of two filters, one operating forwards (increasing t_0), the other backwards (decreasing t_0), this is not very practical. For our purpose the smoother is perhaps best implemented as a conventional least-squares processing of overlapping batches of data, each batch covering an interval of several minutes.

Computing requirements: TBD

FIG. 4. Evolution of the mean error (m.e.) of one component of the attitude vs. time. Top: a (forward) filter uses data up to and including the present time to estimate the attitude. Between star mapper observations the m.e. degrades due to accumulating gyro noise. A smoother (bottom) uses both past and future data and is thus more accurate; it can be thought of as a combination of a forward filter and a backward filter (middle). For real-time attitude determination a forward filter must be used, while a more accurate smoother is preferred for the off-line attitude determination.

4.4. Location estimation

Input for the location estimator are the IDT signal parameters $\underline{b}$, $\underline{G}$, χ^2 , and a model light curve defined by the parameter vector $\underline{q}$:

$$I(H) = q_1 + q_2 \cos(H - q_3) + q_4 \cos(2H - 2q_3) + q_5 \sin(2H - 2q_3).$$

Output are a_0 , a_1 , a_2 defined by the constrained observation equations:

$$N_k \sim a_0 + a_1 I(H - a_2),$$

with mean errors σ_0 , σ_1 , σ_2 and the (constrained) goodness of fit χ^2 .

Trial solutions with many different vectors $\underline{q}$ will be needed for the processing of double stars.

Computing requirements: A FORTRAN mechanization of the basic algorithm (essentially eqns. (3.6.27) - (3.6.29) in /2/), not given in this note, indicates that the equivalent of about 600 additions is needed per frame (four stars).

A.2

```
      DO 5  i = 1, 5
5     bi = bi + Cki*R
      SR = 0.
      DO 6  i = 1, 5
      dd = 0.
      DO 7  j = 1, 5
7     dd = dd + Gij*bj
      di = di + dd
6     SR = SR + ABS(dd)
      IF (SR .GT. EPSILON) GO TO 8
```

c: $\underline{b} = \underline{C}^T \underline{R}$

c: correction vector $\underline{dd} = \underline{F}^{-1} \underline{b}$

c: another iteration needed

Comment: After convergence of the iteration, parameters d_i are transformed to desired vector $\underline{b}$ and the final covariance matrix $\underline{G}$ is computed.

```
      b1 = d1
      b2 = SQRT(d2**2 + d3**2)
      b3 = ATAN2(d3, d2)
      cs = cos b3
      sn = sin b3
      cs2 = cos(2.*b3)
      sn2 = sin(2.*b3)
      b4 = cs2*d4 + sn2*d5
      b5 = cs2*d5 - sn2*d4
      DO 9  i = 1, 5
      DO 9  j = i, 5
9     Fij = 0.
      chi2 = 0.
      DO 10 k = 1, n
      h1 = 1.
      h2 = cs*Ck2 + sn*Ck3
      h3 = d2*Ck3 - d3*Ck2
      h4 = cs2*Ck4 + sn2*Ck5
      h5 = cs2*Ck5 - sn2*Ck4
      E = d1 + d2*Ck2 + d3*Ck3 + d4*Ck4 + d5*Ck5
      DO 11 i = 1, 5
      DO 11 j = i, 5
11     Fij = Fij + hi*hj/E
10     chi2 = chi2 + (Nk - E)**2/E
      CALL INVERT (F, G)
      WRITE b, G, chi2
      END
```

c: arctan in correct quadrant

Number of statements = 63

Arithmetic operation counts (MLFIT)

Execution time for the fitting procedure MLFIT is estimated by counting the number of various arithmetic operations. On the average we shall have $n = 600$ (samples per star per frame). The iterations converge rapidly; let us assume 4 iterations on the average. We find

number of additions or subtractions	$n_{\text{add}} = 61\ 000$
- " - multiplications	$n_{\text{mult}} = 53\ 000$
- " - divisions	$n_{\text{div}} = 24\ 000$
- " - sin/cos/arctan/sqrt	$n_{\text{func}} = 1\ 206$

We have allowed $\frac{1}{2}5^3$ additions and $\frac{1}{2}5^3$ multiplications for each matrix inversion. For simplicity, we shall adopt the relations

$$t_{\text{mult}} = 1.5 t_{\text{add}}, \quad t_{\text{div}} = 4.5 t_{\text{add}}, \quad t_{\text{func}} = 20 t_{\text{add}}.$$

Single precision, i.e. 32 to 36 bits per floating-point number, is sufficient.

The total execution time is then

$$T = 280\ 000 t_{\text{add}}.$$

Since 4 stars must be processed with this routine per frame, and one frame corresponds to 2 sec of observation, we need $t_{\text{add}} < 1.8 \mu\text{s}$ in order that this part of the processing alone shall not take more than 100 % of real time (quasi real-time processing, i.e. with a delay of not more than a few days, is desirable).

APPENDIX B

Modified procedure, MLFIT1

A modified FORTRAN algorithm for estimating $\underline{b}$, $\underline{G}$, and χ^2 (phase bunching)

The underlying idea for this modification is that observation equations with identical modulation phase angle (H_k) can be added with no loss of information (this is a property of the Poisson statistics of counts). In reality it will of course hardly happen that two samples have exactly the same phase. It seems likely however that the loss of information is insignificant if we bunch together equations having the same H_k within (say) $\pm 7.5^\circ$. This should effectively reduce the number of samples to be processed from $n = 600$ to $360^\circ / 15^\circ = 24$, with a corresponding reduction of computations for part of the procedure.

```

DIMENSION N(2400), H(2400), b(5), F(5,5), M(24), C(24,5), d(5), G(5,5)
READ n, N, H
A = 24./6.2831853
DO 1 i = 1, 5
  bi = 0.
DO 11 m = 1, 24
11  Cmi = 0.
    DO 1 j = i, 5
      1  Fij = 0.
    DO 12 m = 1, 24
12  Mm = 0.
    DO 21 k = 1, n
      m = 1 + INT(A*Hk)
      Mm = Mm + Nk
      cs = cos Hk
      sn = sin Hk
      Cm1 = Cm1 + 1.
      Cm2 = Cm2 + cs
      Cm3 = Cm3 + sn
      Cm4 = Cm4 + 1. - 2.*sn**2
21  Cm5 = Cm5 + 2.*sn*cs
    DO 2 k = 1, 24
      DO 2 i = 1, 5
        bi = Cki*Mk/(Mk + 1)
        DO 2 j = 2, 5
          2  Fij = Fij + Cki*Ckj/(Mk + 1)

```

c: we assume $0 \leq H_k < 2\pi$

```
CALL INVERT (F, G)
... etc.
```

The rest is identical to the previous algorithm, except that n is everywhere replaced by 24, and N_k by M_k . Number of statements = 73.

Counting the number of operations we find

```
nadd = 7500
nmult = 5300
ndiv = 960
nfunc = 1206
```

Total execution time: $T = 44\,000 t_{\text{add}}$.

Note that more than half this time is required for the trigonometric functions in the DO 21-loop ($24\,000 t_{\text{add}}$). This could be reduced to about $10\,000 t_{\text{add}}$, e.g. by using polynomial approximations (3rd degree) for sin and cos within each 15° interval (maximum error even with Taylor expansion is $1.2 \cdot 10^{-5}$). The total time is then $T = 30\,000 t_{\text{add}}$, or almost a factor 10 faster than the original procedure MLFIT.